

ANALYSIS OF PRINCIPALS' MANAGERIAL EFFECTIVENESS FOR TEACHERS' JOB COMMITMENT IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study analyzed principals' managerial effectiveness for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 8,989 respondents (263 principals and 5,286 teachers) of public and (686 principals and 2,754 teachers) of private secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample for this study consisted of 899 respondents (26 principals and 528 teachers) of public and (69 principals and 276 teachers) of private secondary schools drawn from 8,989 respondents (263 principals and 5,286 teachers) of public and (686 principals and 2,754 teachers) of private secondary schools using proportionate stratified sampling technique. A researcher-developed questionnaire titled "Principals' Managerial Effectiveness for Teachers' Job Commitment Scale (PMETJCS)" was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one from the Department of Educational Foundations, NnamdiAzikiwe University. Cronbach alpha was used for a test of internal consistency of the instrument which yielded coefficients of 0.81, 0.79 and 0.76 for clusters B1-B3 with an overall coefficient of 0.79 obtained from single administration of 30 copies of the questionnaire to principals and teachers of public and private secondary schools in Enugu State. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test was used to test the hypotheses at .05 alpha level. The findings of the study revealed among others that principals' effectiveness on motivation, communication and discipline for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State were to a high extent. Also, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of all dimensions of principals' managerial effectiveness for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Anambra State Chapter of All Nigeria Conference of Principals of Secondary Schools (ANCOPSS) should organize seminars on disciplinary issues for principals to exchange ideas and upgrade their skills of handling misconduct of teachers in secondary schools.

KEYWORDS

Principals, Managerial Effectiveness, Teachers, Job Commitment, Motivation, Communication, Discipline.

Introduction

Any society striving for restructuring and molding the character of its members economically, socially, morally and emotionally invest hugely in formal education. Formal education is delivered in school settings through primary, secondary and tertiary institutions of learning. The formal learning institution in which learners receive post-basic education is the secondary school.

Secondary education is the intermediary between the primary and tertiary levels of education which train and supply middle-level manpower required for the development of the society. Onyeukwu (2022) opined that secondary education equips its recipients with moral, intellectual honesty, respect for persons, compassion and courage and above all capacity, to live a righteous life. Secondary level of education is categorized into public and private schools.

Public secondary schools are established and controlled by the government through various ministries, commissions or boards, while private secondary schools are established and controlled by individuals, religious bodies and non-government establishment among others. Ilavbare and Nwogbo (2021) asserted that, the public secondary schools are financed by government with taxpayer's money to provide equal education opportunities to everyone, while private secondary schools are established to educate students and make profit. Any public or private secondary school is managed by the principal.

The principal occupies crucial position in a secondary school. Ikenga and Enyi (2021) stressed that principal is the individual vested with the responsibility of ensuring smooth daily operations of secondary school. He is the chief executive officer responsible for the smooth running of the daily affairs of secondary school. The leadership behaviour of the principal and their work attitude influence their managerial effectiveness.

Managerial effectiveness is the optimal utilization of the available resources towards the attainment of the goals of the school. Olorunsola and Belo (2018) defined managerial effectiveness as the ability of an administrator to optimally utilize available human, material and financial resources to attain predetermined organizational goals. It is concerned with attainment of success in leading and influencing subordinate to devote their time and energy to achieve common goals. Nanang, Dedi and Tuty (2021) defined managerial effectiveness as the success attained by administrators through abilities and application of administrative strategies in leading and empowering subordinates to work harder for attainment of set goals of an organization. Operationally, managerial effectiveness is the optimal control of subordinates' activities to bring about improvement on school affairs and administrative tasks through judicious use of the available resources.

Managerial effectiveness of principals could be assessed through a rating of their administrative activities in secondary schools. Kaur and Chadha cited in Pranitasari (2019) noted that managerial effectiveness in an organization could be assessed using the dimensions of their activities such as communication, good interpersonal relationships, discipline, use of resources, conflict resolution, integrity, motivating, delegating, building image, welfare management, availability for consultation, supervision and innovation in an organization. Similarly, Nnebedum, Oshia, Nwanne and Chinagorom (2022) pointed out that, managerial effectiveness of principals could be evaluated through accurate record management, proper management of school facilities, timely communication, judicious management of school financial resources, amicable resolution of conflict, discipline and motivation of staff. The focus of this study is principals' managerial effectiveness on motivation, communication and discipline which are core administrative tasks of creating favourable work environment. The justification for the choice of these seven components is because professional

misconduct and failure to execute assigned tasks could be attributed to managerial ineffectiveness in the areas. The reason for excluding some dimensions of principals' managerial effectiveness in this study is due to the fact that there is absence of peculiar problems in the areas.

Motivation is a drive or anything that induces an individual to exhibit desirable behaviour while engaging in a given activity. The principals can effectively motivate teachers through joint decision making, encouraging them to attend sponsored training programmes, treating them with respect, making available of facilities to them and recognizing their outstanding contributions in the school. Ezema and Ogunshola (2020) outlined effective motivational technique to include: developing of favourable work environment, providing timely information, building cordial interpersonal relationship with staff, praising them for outstanding performance, encouraging teamwork, organizing professional development and improving well-being of subordinates. Motivated staff can put their best efforts and energy to discharge their duties with or without supervision of their activities. Another managerial activity of the principal is communication.

Communication is the act of transmitting or receiving information between two or more persons using words, symbols, signs or in written form. Effective communication entails listening attentively to other during conversation; making use of body languages, speaking in moderate tone and providing of timely feedback. Musa, Yusuf and Mustapha (2021) noted that every organization is in dire need of a wise leader who is visionary, flexible and who will be able to adopt changes and communicate effectively. Effective communication is likely to reduce misunderstanding and conflict. Another managerial activity of the principal is discipline.

Discipline is the state of orderliness and obedience to the guiding principles or laid down rules of an organization. Atanda and Wambugu (2022) defined discipline as a conscious effort geared towards training and developing peoples character to follow an instituted order or an ethical standard of conduct in an organization. The existence of well-disciplined teachers and students as exhibited by conforming to laid down rules, respect of oneself, self-control, orderliness, and displaying acceptable patterns of the behaviour is one of the indicators of principals' managerial effectiveness. Olorunsola and Belo (2018) stated that well-disciplined teachers comply with schools rules, regulations and policies which improve their job commitment. This study analyzed principals' managerial effectiveness for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State.

Teachers' job commitment is their engagement in statutory obligations in the school. Onafowo, Egwunyenga and Oweikpodor (2023) defined teachers' job commitment as the willingness of teaching staff to put their efforts and time in performing their duties. Teachers' job commitment is the state of being loyal and devoted in executing instructional responsibilities in the school. Odoh and Nwite (2022) defined teachers' job commitment as their dedication, attachment and involvement in their work or duties in order to accomplish task and achieve positive outcomes or good results. Teachers' job commitment is the dedication of teaching staff towards their duties. Contextually, teachers' job commitment is the work attitude and behaviour exhibited by teaching staff towards attainment of predetermined educational goals and objectives.

In this study, teachers' job commitment was measured with the following indices. Teachers who are committed to their job are punctual to work, deliver instruction at the stipulated period, cover scheme of work and participate in school functions. Oredein and Ebo (2021) opined that, a teacher who is committed and loyal to his or her job exhibits positive behaviours at school such as punctuality, dedication to school work, making extra time for students after school hours, implementing diverse teaching methods in the classroom, and improvising instructional materials

when they are not available. Committed teachers comply to professional code of conduct and maintain high level of discipline.

The discipline and administrative problems that dominate public and privates secondary schools in Anambra State could indicates managerial ineffectiveness of the principals. Olorunsola and Belo (2018) noted that, in Nigeria secondary schools, there is an increasing public fear and complaints about managerial ineffectiveness of principals as showed by escalation of the incidence of cultism, delinquent behaviour, truancy and misconduct of students and teachers caused by principals' leadership style, communication behaviours, work attitude and disciplinary actions.

The managerial effectiveness of the principals in both public and private secondary schools could be deduced from academic achievement of students in West Africa Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSEC) results. The difference in the mode of operations in public and private secondary schools could also be attributed to the difference in managerial effectiveness of the principals who oversee and ensure smooth running of the daily affairs of the two categories of schools. Agundu and Onyali (2020) noted that, private secondary schools are managed by their school principals using different educational philosophy as they deemed suitable to improve their managerial effectiveness.

The principals of public and private secondary schools seem to apply different managerial approaches due to the variation in their philosophy and ideology. Atanda and Wambugu (2022) noted that, approaches of management in public secondary schools are quite relaxed and easy than the approaches used in private secondary schools which are quite harsh. As result of these approaches of managing disciplinary problems, motivation and supervision of teachers in public and private secondary schools appear to differ. Atanda and Wambugu stressed that, leaving the school before the closing time, going late for lesson, coming late to school and absent from school without approvals are mostly found in public schools, while avoiding school assembly, leaving a duty post and form of trading among teachers predominately form of indiscipline in private secondary schools in Nigeria. The varying nature of policy, rules, programmes, grants and supports receive in public and private secondary schools could bring difference in the approaches of supervision and communication. It is based on this background that the study analyzed principals' managerial effectiveness for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The scenarios of some teachers sneaking out of school during official hours to attend to their personal affairs, presenting ill-prepared lessons, exhibiting of poor role models to students, absenting from school and classes makes one wonders if they are committed to their job in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State. The uncommitted attitude of teachers towards their job may be attributed to the existence of conflict, indiscipline, poor record management, low rapport, and ill-motivation of teachers in public and private secondary schools in the state. The incessant cases of failure of teachers to effectively execute tasks assigned to them could be traceable to poor delegation of duties approaches of public and private secondary schools' principals in Anambra State.

Teachers' adherence to professional ethics and work attitude in public and private secondary schools is shaped by their irrespective rules and regulations. Public and private secondary schools have varied rules and procedures for taking disciplinary action which could account for dissimilarity in the punctuality, absenteeism, and habitual lateness to work among teachers in the types of school. Finances and high staff strengths of public secondary schools seem to be utilized by principals to improve their managerial effectiveness than their counterpart in private schools. The principals of

public secondary schools appear to put into judicious use of the available funds to induce the dedication of teachers towards their duties to improve managerial effectiveness than their private counterparts. It is against this backdrop that this study was conceived by the researcher.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to analyze principals' managerial effectiveness for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to analysis the extent of

1. Principals' effectiveness on motivation for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Principals' effectiveness on communication for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State.
1. Principals' effectiveness on discipline for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the extent of principals' effectiveness on motivation for teachers' job commitment of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the extent of principals' effectiveness on communication for teachers' job commitment of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. What is the extent of principals' effectiveness on discipline for teachers' job commitment of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' in public and private secondary schools of their effectiveness on motivation for teachers' job commitment in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' in public and private secondary schools of their effectiveness on communication for teachers' job commitment in Anambra State.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' in public and private secondary schools of their effectiveness on discipline for teachers' job commitment in Anambra State

Methods

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. According to Asenahabi (2019), descriptive survey research design is the one that involves numeric depiction of attitudes, opinions or trends of a population by studying a sample. This design is deemed appropriate for the study, since the researcher collected data which described the opinions of the given sample of the population on principals' managerial effectiveness for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State. The study was carried out in Anambra State. The choice of Anambra State as the area of the study is justified by the cases of lateness, absenteeism and other forms of misconduct among some teachers probably due to managerial ineffectiveness of the public and private school principals in the state.

The population of the study comprised 8,989 respondents (263 principals and 5,286 teachers) of public secondary schools and (686 principals and 2,754 teachers) of private secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. The sample for this study consisted of 899 respondents (26 principals and 528 teachers) of public secondary schools and (69 principals and 276 teachers) of private secondary schools drawn using proportionate stratified sampling technique. The sample comprised 10% of the entire population of teachers from Aguata, Awka, Nnewi, Ogidi, Onitsha and Otuocha education zones respectively. The 10% of the population is in line with Nwana cited in Adekeye and Apeh (2019) who opined that if the population is a few hundreds, a 40% or more sample will do; if many hundreds, a 20% sample will do; if a few thousands, a 10% sample will do and if several thousands, a 5% or less sample will do. Since the population is in few thousands, the researcher will draw 10% which can be conveniently and adequately managed.

A researcher-developed questionnaire titled ‘‘Principals’ Managerial Effectiveness for Teachers’ Job Commitment Scale (PMETJCS)’’ was used for data collection. The instrument was developed by the researcher based on review of related literature and consultation of experts in educational management. It has two versions. One version of the instrument was responded to by the principals while the other was responded to by teachers. This was done to checkmate the principals’ responses. Each of the two versions has two sections A and B. Section A elicits information on demographic data of respondents such as type of school.

Section B of PMETJCS has seven clusters namely: B1 to B3. These clusters were based on the seven areas of managerial effectiveness for teachers’ job commitment covered in the study. Cluster B1 has nine items on managerial effectiveness on motivation for teachers’ job commitment; cluster B2 has seven items on managerial effectiveness on communication for teachers’ job commitment and Cluster B3 has eight items on managerial effectiveness on discipline for teachers’ job commitment. The instrument therefore contains a total of 24 items which are structured on a four point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts, two in the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one in Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education, NnamdiAzikiwe University, Awka. The researcher presented the title, purpose of the study, research questions and hypotheses with a copy of the questionnaire to the three experts and requested them to examine and scrutinize the items in terms of relevance, suitability, clarity of instruction and content coverage. The experts suggested among others that double-barrel items should be structured and proper editorial should be done on the instrument. Based on the suggestions, the instrument was properly edited and double-barrel items should be separated. Thus, their suggestions were used to produce the final version of the instrument.

Cronbach alpha method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument. The coefficient obtained for clusters B1-B3 of the section B were 0.81, 0.79 and 0.76 respectively and overall coefficient was 0.79. Thus, the researcher considered the instrument to be reliable for the study. This is in line with Taber (2018) who recommended that co-efficient value of 0.75 and above is adequate for any research work.

The researcher with the help of five research assistants who are secondary school teachers in Anambra State used direct approach for data collection. The research assistants were briefed by the researcher on the nature of the study and how to approach the respondents for data

collection. A total of 899 copies of the questionnaire were distributed, 554 copies to 26 principals and 528 teachers in public secondary schools, while 345 copies to 69 principals and 276 teachers in private secondary schools. Out of these, a total of 876 copies of questionnaire of which 548 copies were from respondents (26 principals and 522 teachers) in public secondary schools, while 328 copies were from respondents (69 principals and 259 teachers) in private secondary schools were properly filled and successfully retrieved, indicating 97% percent return. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and one tailed independent t-test was used to test the hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The decision on the research questions were based on range of values obtained from mean scores. Thus, mean scores ranging 3.50-4.00 indicates VHE, 2.50-3.49 indicates HE, 1.50-2.49 indicate LE, and 1.00-1.49 indicates VLE respectively. For decisions on the hypotheses, where p-value is equal to or less than level of significant value of 0.05 ($P \leq .05$), the null hypothesis was rejected but where p-value is greater than level of significant value of 0.05 ($P > .05$), the null hypotheses was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the extent of principals' effectiveness on motivation for teachers' job commitment of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on Principals' Effectiveness on Motivation for Teachers' Job Commitment

S/N	ITEMS	Respondents from public secondary schools (n = 548)			Respondents from private secondary schools (n =328)		
		$\bar{x}$	SD	Remark	$\bar{x}$	SD	Remark
1	Use constant words of encouragement to induce exceptional performance among teachers	2.84	1.04	High Extent	2.71	1.10	High Extent
2	Applaud teachers who attain higher job engagement	2.79	1.09	High Extent	2.62	1.04	High Extent
3	Grant work autonomy to teachers to encourage them develop innovative ideas in discharging their duties	2.46	1.00	Low Extent	2.40	1.08	Low Extent
4	Issue monetary reward to teachers that complete their scheme of work at stipulated time	2.44	0.98	Low Extent	2.47	1.06	Low Extent
5	Issue letter of commendations issue to exceptional teachers to make them devote more time in discharging their duties	2.57	1.02	High Extent	2.71	1.11	High Extent
6	Sponsor teachers to attend conferences of Professional Associations to enrich learning experience of students in the classroom	2.62	1.05	High Extent	2.68	1.08	High Extent
7	Compensate teachers for overtime work done encourage hard work	2.51	1.09	High Extent	2.49	1.13	Low Extent
8	Issue bonuses to teachers for goal achievement on regular basis	2.66	1.06	High Extent	2.81	0.95	High Extent
9	Give handshake to teachers as a way of showing gratitude for their positive contributions improve their productivity	2.77	0.99	High Extent	2.60	0.93	High Extent
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		2.63	1.04	High Extent	2.61	1.05	High Extent

Table 1 revealed that the mean scores of respondents in both public and private secondary schools for items 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9 fell within the mean range of 2.50-2.49 indicating high extent of principals' effectiveness on motivation for teachers' job commitment with regards to the items. The mean scores of the respondents in both public and private secondary schools for items 3 and 4 fell within the mean range of 1.50-2.49 indicating that there was low extent of principals' effectiveness on motivation for teachers' job commitment with regards to the items. On the other hand, the mean score of respondents from public secondary schools for item 7 indicated high extent of principals' effectiveness on motivation for teachers' job commitment with regards to the item, while that of their counterparts in private secondary schools indicated low extent.

The overall standard deviation scores of 1.04 and 1.05 for respondents in public and private secondary schools respectively indicated that their responses are close to the mean, implying that the respondents are homogenous in their responses amongst cluster. The cluster mean of 2.63 and 2.61 obtained for respondents in public and private secondary schools respectively fell within the range 2.50-3.49. Thus, principals' effectiveness on motivation for teachers' job commitment of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State was to high extent.

Hypothesis 1

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' effectiveness on motivation for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 2: The Summary of t-test Analysis no Significant Difference in the Mean Ratings of Principals' Effectiveness on Motivation for Teachers' Job Commitment in Public and Private Secondary Schools (n =876)

Group	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	p-value	Df	α	Remark
Public Secondary Schools	548	2.63	1.04	0.20	874	0.05	Not Significant
Private Secondary Schools	328	2.61	1.05				

Table 2 revealed that the p-value of 0.20 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' effectiveness on motivation for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What is the extent of principals' effectiveness on communication for teachers' job commitment of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on Principals' Effectiveness on Communication for Teachers' Job Commitment

S/N	ITEMS	Respondents for public secondary schools (n = 548)			Respondents from private secondary schools (n =328)		
		$\bar{x}$	SD	Remark	$\bar{x}$	SD	Remark
10	Listen attentively to teachers during interaction	2.65	1.07	High Extent	2.71	1.04	High Extent
11	Speak clearly to the understanding of staff	2.77	0.98	High Extent	2.84	1.00	High Extent
12	Make use of right choice of words during conversation with staff	2.60	1.02	High Extent	2.56	1.10	High Extent

13	Ask pertinent questions while interacting with teachers	2.81	1.09	High Extent	2.79	1.01	High Extent
14	Make use of eye contacts while discussing with teachers	2.68	1.07	High Extent	2.74	0.98	High Extent
15	Give timely feedback on issues discussed with members of staff	2.46	1.14	Low Extent	2.45	1.02	Low Extent
16	Successfully disseminate information to teachers through electronic devices	2.54	0.99	High Extent	2.53	1.13	High Extent
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		2.64	1.05	High Extent	2.66	1.04	High Extent

Table 2 revealed that both respondents from public and private secondary schools indicated high extent of principals' effectiveness on communication for teachers' job commitment for all items as shown by their mean ratings between 2.50 and 3.49 with exception of item 15. The overall standard deviation scores of 1.05 and 1.04 for respondents in public and private secondary schools respectively indicate convergence of their responses and thus their responses were little clustered around the mean. The cluster mean values of 2.64 for respondents in public schools and 2.66 for respondents in private school which fell within the decision rule of 2.50-3.49 indicated principals' effectiveness on communication for teachers' job commitment of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State was to high extent.

Hypothesis 2

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' effectiveness on communication for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: The Summary of t-test Analysis no Significant Difference in the Mean Ratings of Principals' Effectiveness on Communication for Teachers' Job Commitment in Public and Private Secondary Schools (n = 876)

Group	N	X	SD	p-value	Df	∞	Remark
Public Secondary Schools	548	2.64	1.05	0.17	874	0.05	Not Significant
Private Secondary Schools	328	2.66	1.04				

Table 4 revealed that the p-value of 0.17 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' effectiveness on communication for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 3: What is the extent of principals' effectiveness on discipline for teachers' job commitment of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 5: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on Principals' Effectiveness on Discipline for Teachers' Job Commitment

S/N	ITEMS	Respondents for public secondary schools (n = 548)	Respondents from private secondary schools (n =328)
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		$\bar{x}$	SD	Remark	$\bar{x}$	SD	Remark
17	Establish rules to guide the professional conduct of teachers	2.67	1.04	High Extent	2.57	1.06	High Extent
18	Issue query to erring staff to dampen further misconduct	2.59	0.95	High Extent	2.62	1.09	High Extent
19	Successfully control the conduct of misbehaved staff through counselling	2.36	1.12	Low Extent	2.33	1.07	Low Extent
20	Give fair hearing before taking disciplinary actions against misbehaved teachers	2.37	1.02	Low Extent	2.34	1.11	Low Extent
21	Discourage misconduct among staff through oral caution	2.76	1.08	High Extent	2.67	1.14	High Extent
22	Use threats to control unacceptable behaviour among teachers	2.81	1.05	High Extent	2.89	1.06	High Extent
23	Instruct misbehaved staff to sign letter of undertaken to discourage the repetition of a particular misconduct	2.64	1.06	High Extent	2.71	0.96	High Extent
24	Organise schedule of follow-up to monitoring staff involve in the same kind of gross professional misconduct control their conducts	2.46	1.15	Low Extent	2.41	1.07	Low Extent
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		2.58	1.06	High Extent	2.57	1.07	High Extent

Table 3 shows that the mean ratings of respondents in both public and private secondary schools for items 17, 18, 21, 22 and 23 were between 2.50 and 3.49 indicating that there was high extent of principals' effectiveness on conflict management in connection to the items. The mean ratings of respondents in both public and private secondary schools which were between 1.50 and 2.49 for items 19, 20 and 25 indicated that there was low extent of principals' effectiveness on discipline for teachers' job commitment.

The pooled standard deviation scores which stood at 1.06 and 1.07 indicated that the mean scores of respondents in public and private secondary schools were clustered and this indicated that a little variation from their responses. The cluster mean values of 2.58 for respondents in public schools and 2.57 for respondents in private schools which fell within the decision rule of 2.50-3.49 indicated principals' effectiveness on discipline for teachers' job commitment of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State was to high extent.

Hypothesis 3

Ho₃: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' effectiveness on discipline for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: The Summary of t-test Analysis no Significant Difference in the Mean Ratings of Principals' Effectiveness on Discipline for Teachers' Job Commitment in Public and Private Secondary Schools (n = 876)

Group	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	p-value	Df	∞	Remark
Public Secondary Schools	548	2.58	1.06	0.24	874	0.05	Not Significant
Private Secondary Schools	328	2.57	1.07				

Table 6 revealed that the p-value of 0.24 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' effectiveness on discipline for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion of the Finding

The finding of the study indicated that principals' effectiveness on motivation for teachers' job commitment of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State was to high extent. This agreed with the finding of Ozkan and Tokel (2018) which indicated that there was high level of managerial effectiveness of school administrators on motivation. The secondary school settings in which the studies were conducted could explain the agreement in findings. The finding disagreed with that of Kokila and Muralidaran (2015) which showed that managerial effectiveness of executives on motivation was low. The difference in time span which might likely influence motivational practices could explain the disagreement in the findings. The finding is an indication that principals of public and private secondary schools to high extent use constant words of encouragement, applaud teachers who attain higher job engagement, issue letter of commendations, bonuses and handshake to teachers to enhance their job commitment. The principals' of public and private secondary schools recorded high extent of effectiveness on motivation possibly due to the fact that it is means of boosting the morale of teachers to work harder for overall success of the institutions. The motivation of teachers makes them feel supported and appreciated which induce high level of job commitment.

Further result indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' effectiveness on motivation for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in line with the finding of Ogbiji (2018) which indicated there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' effectiveness on motivation in public and private secondary schools. This refuted the finding of Azaliwa and Casmir (2016) which indicated that there was a statistical significant difference between the mean ratings of respondents of public and private secondary schools on their effectiveness of motivation for improving teachers' job performance. The difference in the locations and time span of the studies could contribute to the disagreement in the findings. The energy and enthusiastic that could be exhibited by motivated teachers could account for the no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' effectiveness on motivation for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State.

The result of the study showed that principals' effectiveness on communication for teachers' job commitment of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State was to high extent. This supported the finding of Abeer (2020) which showed that the extent of principals' effectiveness on communication in secondary schools was high. This contradicted the finding of Fonceca, Raj and Anandan (2017) which indicated a low level of managerial effectiveness on communication. This is also in disagreement with the finding of Shraddha (2014) who reported that subordinates' opinions about their managers' effectiveness on communication was low. The difference in time span which is associated with changes in communication practices could be connected to the disagreement in the findings. The finding revealed that principals of public and private secondary schools to high extent listen attentively to teachers during interaction, speak clearly to the understanding of staff, make use of right choice of words during conversation with staff, ask pertinent questions while interacting with teachers, make use of eye contacts while discussing with teachers and successfully disseminate information to teachers through electronic devices. This finding could be explained by the fact that principals rely on communication to instruct, direct and guide the activities of teachers to improve

their job commitment. The effectiveness of principals on communication contribute to job commitment by disseminating information about exact tasks which are required of teachers, how and when to execute the tasks.

It was also found that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' effectiveness on communication for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in line with the finding of Aja-Okorie and Usulor (2016) which showed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of public and private secondary school principals on their extent of effectiveness on communication. The similarity in the participants of the study could be attributed to the agreement in the findings of the study. The principals' effectiveness on communication which enables teachers have a clear understanding of work expected of them to perform are likely to improve their commitment in discharging their duties

It was revealed that principals' effectiveness on discipline for teachers' job commitment of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State was to high extent. This disagreed with the finding of Fonceca, Raj and Anandan (2017) which indicated a low level of managerial effectiveness on discipline. The studies were conducted in different organizations and geographical locations which could account for the disagreement. This finding showed that principals establish rules to guide the professional conduct of teachers, issue query to erring staff to dampen further misconduct, discourage misconduct among staff through oral caution, use threats to control unacceptable behaviour among teachers and instruct misbehaved staff to sign letter of undertaken to discourage the repetition of a particular misconduct to a high extent. The principals of public and private secondary schools probably exhibited effectiveness on discipline to ensure teachers behave in a desirable way in the workplace. Principals' effectiveness on discipline helps to ensure that teachers adhere to rules, regulations and procedures that are deemed necessary for enhancing their job commitment in public and private secondary schools.

Further analysis indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' effectiveness on discipline for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State. This contradicted the findings of Atanda and Wambugu (2021) which indicated that there was significant difference in the mean ratings of discipline effectiveness in public and private secondary schools. The contradiction in the findings could be attributed to difference in the geographical locations of the studies. The silence and orderly work environment in which every administrator desire to create could contribute to the no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals' effectiveness on discipline for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that principals to high extent exhibited managerial effectiveness for teachers' job commitment in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State. Principals of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State effectively communicate, discipline and motivate members of staff to improve their job commitment. Principals' managerial effectiveness contributes to efficient and timely accomplishment of tasks to achieve predetermined goals and objectives of secondary education in public and private schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Principals of public and private should constitute staff welfare units saddled with the responsibility of planning and promoting motivation of teachers to enhance their job commitment in secondary schools.
2. Principals of public and private should develop an “open-door” policy that encourages exchange of ideas and dissemination of information which improve their effectiveness on communication for teachers’ job commitment in schools.
3. Anambra State Chapter of All Nigeria Conference of Principals of Secondary Schools (ANCOPSS) should organize seminars on disciplinary issues for principals to exchange ideas and upgrade their skills of handling misconduct of teachers in secondary schools.

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